

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No. B447
Date: 08 May 2009
Take Off: 04:34:59Z
Landing: 09:17:56Z
Flight Time 4h 42m 57s

Campaign: MEVEX Dust Flight 6
Operating Area: Wahiba Sands, Low level area 1, Oman

POB	Position	Name	Institute	Logs y/n
1	Captain	Alan Foster	Directflight	
2	Co-pilot	Ian Ramsay-Rae	Directflight	
3	CCM	Gaynor Ottaway	Directflight	
4	Mission Scientist	Dave Pollard	Met Office	
5	Flight Manager	Mo Smith	FAAM	Y
6	Core Chem / AVAPS	Kate Turnbull	FAAM	Y
7	Cloud Physics	Martyn Pickering	Met Office	y
8	ARIES	Stuart Rogers	Met Office	
9	SWS / SHIMS	Martin Glew	Met Office	
10	Wet Neph / CVI / IIR	Andy Wilson	Met Office	
11	MARSS	Rob King	Met Office	
12	Filters	Anne Klaver	University of Paris	
13	Mini-LIDAR	Joss Kent	Met Office	
14	Observer 1	Steve Walters	RAF	
15	Observer 2	Steve Brown	RAF	
16				
17				
18				
19				

Missing Log Sheet	Reason
Core Chemistry / TDLAS	no In Flight log except in cases of instrument problems
AVAPS	No completed log available so far
PSAP log	No log as PSAP pump/filter info included on Flight Summary page
Wet Neph	Awaiting confirmation of whether a log was created
CVI	Awaiting confirmation of whether a log was created
SWS	Awaiting confirmation of whether a log was created
Mini-LIDAR	Awaiting confirmation of whether a log was created

Revision	Date	Author	Comments
r0	31 Dec 2009	Doug Anderson	Initial version missing the above noted logs
r1			
r2			

VIDEO RECORDINGS:

The following avi format video recordings should be available at the BADC in core_processed/faam-video :

faam-video-dfc_faam_20090508_r0_b447_044724_1hz.avi
 faam-video-dfc_faam_20090508_r0_b447_054724_1hz.avi
 faam-video-dfc_faam_20090508_r0_b447_060332_1hz.avi
 faam-video-dfc_faam_20090508_r0_b447_063300_1hz.avi
 faam-video-dfc_faam_20090508_r0_b447_065104_1hz.avi
 faam-video-dfc_faam_20090508_r0_b447_075104_1hz.avi
 faam-video-dfc_faam_20090508_r0_b447_081401_1hz.avi

faam-video-ffc_faam_20090508_r0_b447_062442_1hz.avi
 faam-video-ffc_faam_20090508_r0_b447_063255_1hz.avi
 faam-video-ffc_faam_20090508_r0_b447_065107_1hz.avi
 faam-video-ffc_faam_20090508_r0_b447_075107_1hz.avi
 faam-video-ffc_faam_20090508_r0_b447_081354_1hz.avi

faam-video-ffc_faam_20090508_r0_b447_044718_1hz.avi
 faam-video-ffc_faam_20090508_r0_b447_054718_1hz.avi
 faam-video-ffc_faam_20090508_r0_b447_060327_1hz.avi

faam-video-ufc_faam_20090508_r0_b447_050216_25hz.avi
 faam-video-ufc_faam_20090508_r0_b447_062903_25hz.avi
 faam-video-ufc_faam_20090508_r0_b447_063949_25hz.avi
 faam-video-ufc_faam_20090508_r0_b447_071250_25hz.avi
 faam-video-ufc_faam_20090508_r0_b447_081358_25hz.avi

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Cloud Physics Processing	Probably no processing log for these flights.
AVAPS	No completed log available so far
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 faam-video-dfc_faam_20090508_r0_b447_065104_1hz.avi
 faam-video-dfc_faam_20090508_r0_b447_075104_1hz.avi
 faam-video-dfc_faam_20090508_r0_b447_081401_1hz.avi

faam-video-ffc_faam_20090508_r0_b447_062442_1hz.avi
 faam-video-ffc_faam_20090508_r0_b447_063255_1hz.avi
 faam-video-ffc_faam_20090508_r0_b447_065107_1hz.avi
 faam-video-ffc_faam_20090508_r0_b447_075107_1hz.avi
 faam-video-ffc_faam_20090508_r0_b447_081354_1hz.avi

faam-video-ffc_faam_20090508_r0_b447_044718_1hz.avi
 faam-video-ffc_faam_20090508_r0_b447_054718_1hz.avi
 faam-video-ffc_faam_20090508_r0_b447_060327_1hz.avi

faam-video-ufc_faam_20090508_r0_b447_050216_25hz.avi
 faam-video-ufc_faam_20090508_r0_b447_062903_25hz.avi
 faam-video-ufc_faam_20090508_r0_b447_063949_25hz.avi
 faam-video-ufc_faam_20090508_r0_b447_071250_25hz.avi
 faam-video-ufc_faam_20090508_r0_b447_081358_25hz.avi

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No B447
 Date: 08 May 2009
 Project: MEVEX, IASI Overpass
 Location: Wahiba Sands, Area 1, Oman

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
031525		Start-Up	0.22 kft	266	23'35.36N, 58'17.65E
042658	042953	Pirouette 1	0.20 kft	091	Mag Hdg 090
043041		ASP	0.20 kft	078	Open
043459		T/O	2.0 kft	274	Muscat
044735		Video	18.5 kft	174	Start FFC & DFC
050055	051513	Run 1	29.0 kft	154	B*-A*
050220		Video	29.0 kft	155	Start Spotter
051622	051843	Orbit 1	29.1 - 28.9 kft	137	40deg, left, st140
052316	054207	Run 2	29.0 kft	321	
052330		Sonde	29.0 kft	327	Launch #01
052916		Sonde	29.0 kft	333	Launch #02
053300		Satellite	29.0 kft	333	IASI Overpass
053518		Sonde	29.0 kft	333	Launch #03, failed
054101		Sonde	29.0 kft	334	Launch #04
055029	060752	Profile 1	29.0 - 11.3 kft	154	
060942	061503	Profile 1	11.3 - 6.2 kft	324	QNH1005, 11k'-6k'
061507	061724	Profile 2	6.2 - 8.2 kft	336	6k-8k'
061724	063329	Run 3	8.2 kft	338	8k', A*
063334	063654	Profile 3	8.2 - 5.3 kft	336	8k-5k'
064022	064425	Profile 3	5.3 - 2.8 kft	159	5k-2.5k' on Q1005
064200		Event	4.0 kft	152	500fpm from 4k'
064425	070038	Run 4	2.8 kft	156	4k-2.5k'
065421		Event	2.8 kft	156	Coasting out
070043	070530	Profile 4	2.7 - 0.55 kft	156	2.5k-500'
070840	070935	Profile 4	0.50 - 0.19 kft	325	500-100' on Q101
070935	071646	Run 5	0.19 - 0.37 kft	327	100' on Q1013
071022		Heimann	0.18 kft	330	Cal 25-32C
071646		Profile 5	0.32 kft	334	to 1.5k' twds coast 071819
Event		1.0 kft	327		Coasting in
071923	073147	Run 6	1.6 kft	332	Over land, end at B*
073332	074703	Run 7	1.5 kft	125	Azimuth run
073525		Event	1.6 kft	144	End azimuth
074653		Event	1.6 kft	156	Coasting out
074714	074955	Profile 6	1.5 - 0.20 kft	157	1.5k-100'
074956	075424	Run 8	0.20 - 0.28 kft	149	100', Q1011
075236		Heimann	0.22 kft	150	Cal 25-32C
075432	075849	Profile 7	0.32 - 2.5 kft	152	100-3k'
080114	080528	Profile 7	2.5 - 6.1 kft	328	2.5k-6k'
080528	082156	Run 9	6.1 kft	336	Q1011
081147		Event	6.1 kft	335	Coasting in
082551	083355	Profile 8	6.1 - 13.2 kft	148	6k'- 13k', Q1005
083809	084503	Profile 8	13.3 - 20.0 kft	340	
084650		Video	20.0 kft	348	Stop Recording
091756		Land	0.23 kft	179	Muscat
043041		ASP	0.20 kft	078	Close
092003	092309	Pirouette 2	0.23 kft	180	180
092647		Shutdown	0.24 kft	266	23'35.36N, 58'17.66E

B447 02:11:22-09:26:55

GLNG_PARA0581, GLAT_PARA0580

Pilot: Cpt Luc Lathouwers

NavData Cycle 2009-4 Expires: Thursday, 07 May 2009.

Scale: 1:2470000 (1 inch = 33.88 naut mi). Printed on 07 May 2009

5 4 7 7 4 9 4 6

FliteStar 9.4.5.0

MEVEX – IASI Sortie – B447
Date: 8th May 2009
Mission Scientist: Dave Pollard

T/O OOMS: 04:35Z (08:35 local)
Land OOMS: 08:40Z (12:40 local)

Location: Wahibah Sands low level area 1
 Between - Point A: 20°30'N 59°30'E and Point B: 22°00'N 58°40'E

Coordinating with IASI overpass at 05:33Z

Weather: Cloud free conditions, moderate aerosol loadings

Sortie Aim: To validate IASI retrievals and forecasts of moderate aerosol conditions.

Key Instruments: ARIES, MARSS, SWS/SHIMS, IR Cameras, Mini Lidar, Small particulate probes, AVAPS, Nephs, Core Chem

Sortie profile:

Detail	Item time	Running time	Local time
Perform pirouette before take-off			
Take off OOMS		04:35:00	08:35:00
Transit to operating area at FL270	00:25:00	05:00:00	09:00:00
Fly straight and level run at FL270 between points B* and A*	00:15:00	05:15:00	09:15:00
Perform 1 orbit	00:05:00	05:20:00	09:20:00
SLR at FL260 A* to B* dropping 4 sondes	00:15:00	05:35:00	09:35:00
Profile descent, from B* to A*, to FL150 or other suitable level	00:15:00	05:50:00	09:50:00
Straight and level run at FL150 A* to B*	00:20:00	06:10:00	10:10:00
Profile descent to 8000ft or other suitable level B* to A*	00:10:00	06:20:00	10:20:00
Straight and level run at 8000ft to A* to B*	00:15:00	06:35:00	10:35:00
Profile descent to 1500ft B* to A*	00:15:00	06:50:00	10:50:00
Straight and level run at 1500ft to A* to B*	00:20:00	07:10:00	11:10:00
Perform 2 SLRs at 1500ft to arrive back at B*	00:45:00	07:55:00	11:55:00
Profile ascent to transit alt between B and A	00:20:00	08:15:00	12:15:00
Transit back to OOMS	00:25:00	08:40:00	12:40:00
Perform pirouette after landing			
Total sortie time		04:05:00	04:05:00

Mission Scientist's Debrief – B447 MEVEX
8th May 2009
David Pollard

Sortie Aim:

B447 was yet another visit to the Ramlat al Wahibah region to characterise the atmospheric column, its dust loading and their radiative properties as well as surface emission in conjunction with an overpass of METOP.

Weather:

There were clear skies for most of the operating area, apart from a patch of ~2-3/8 Cu over the sea, ~5 miles away from the coast, which slowly burnt off during the day. Winds were fresh, with a considerable sheer.

Sortie overview:

A Pirouette was performed before take off with some Ci about, but clear of the sun. The ascent from Muscat showed good aerosol loadings (~200/m Neph scattering), with some structure, to 10000 ft with some remnants to higher levels, PCASP reporting ~40/cc at FL200.

The initial climb was to FL290 at point B* (A* and B* were on the leg from A to B which had been used extensively during the campaign) where a run was conducted to the South where some Cu was seen below over the sea (Photos 1-3) at A* a 40° orbit was performed to allow SWS to look down at the dust before running back to the North at FL290, dropping 4 sondes to coincide with the METOP overpass.

This was followed by a profile down to find some interesting layers to investigate. On the way down, Neph scattering started to increase at 14000 ft. The profile was initially down to 6000 ft before returning to 8000 ft for the highest loadings with Neph scattering ~200/m with some spectral separation, PCASP at 650/cc and CDP showing 4.8 thicker dust was found at the southern end of the run over the sea.

The next level was chosen to be 2500 ft, hoping to target a clear slot between layers. At the northern end of the run, the upper and lower layers appeared to have merged, but as we made our way to the south the Neph scattering steadily decreased and, visually, we appeared to be in a clear slot (Photo 4).

We then profiled down to 100ft and started a run in towards the coast with the Neph showing a large spectral separation, blue over red. On coasting in and climbing to 1500 ft, the Neph scattering and separation reduced. The start of the run on the reciprocal at 1500ft was a short azimuth run for SWS before turning back onto heading. During this run, the PCASP concentrations were around 500/cc and steady. On coasting out we again dropped to 100ft and the strong Neph separation returned.

This was followed by a profile to 6000 ft with the strong Neph separation remaining until the Neph scattering dropped off at around 2000 ft. Cloud bases were ~1000 ft and tops at ~1500 ft. At 4400 ft we started to penetrate the next dust layer and established on a straight and level run at 6000 ft with the Neph scattering steady at 200/m throughout. We then profiled up over the operating area encountering a good peak in the aerosol loadings at 9000 ft (Neph: 400/m, CDP: 2) which was stronger than experienced on the initial descent into the area which was coincident with elevated CO and O3.

After landing at Muscat we performed a pirouette under clear skies.

Summary:

Another good sortie over the Ramlat al Wahibah and Arabian sea with moderate aerosol loadings with well stratified structure and horizontal homogeneity, in contrast to previous visits to the area. Some cloud at the southern end of the area could cause some problems with retrievals.

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B.447** Date 8/5/9 Name Pohard Page 1 of 4

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
04:26:59			E		Pirouette some Ci
04:29:53					end
04:35 -					T/O
04:45					Good Neph cloudings to 10kft - 200 m ⁻¹ - some structure
		FL200			Neph almost to 0, seeming fairly clean around, not much Ci (COP 1.4 in profile) PCASP 40 cc ⁻¹ now
		FL220			entering moisture layer Lidar top of layer ~ 14 kft clear above cloud
05:00:55	R1	FL290	135	135 13X	Short peak in Neph and GO
05:15:13	R1				end - Some AB below
05:16:22	O1		140	A*	40° L Photos ①, ② & ③ showing cloud
05:18:10	O1				end 2 layers 18kft 5.5 km } below 6.5 km } 21.5kft
05:23:30	R2	FL290	325	A	Sonde 1 AC mainly over sea a few miles off coast

05:29:16

nothing over cloud
Sonde 2

Mission Scientist's Log

30 x 8

Flight No **B**.....⁴⁴⁷ Date 8/5/18 Name Pothard Page 2 of 4

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
05:35:18					Sonde 3 - Lemon
05:41:01					Sonde 4
05:42:07	R2			B ³⁶	end
05:50:29	P1	FL200	150	B ³⁶ 104	
		FL140			Neph increasing
06:07:52	P1				Interrupt
06:15:	"1/R2	6000ft			Climbing to 8ft for best reading
06:17:24	P2/P3	8000ft			Neph ~ 200m + sep CFC 4.8 PCASP 650 Surface layer higher over land 2km below 6.6 1.4 thicker over sea
06:40:27					
06:33:29	R3				end
06:33:34	P3	8000ft			
06:36:54					Int
06:40:22					start
06:44:25	P3/P4	2500ft	155	B ³⁶ 104	Hopefully flying towards clear sky, Neph falling steadily photo (4)
06:57					Lider layer 250m below thickest 400m below
07:00:08	R4/P4	2500ft ↓ 1500ft			Neph increasing

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B.447** Date 8/5/01 Name Polard Page 3 of 4

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
07:05:30					Profile interrupted, w/ oil tanker was just after
07:08:10	R4	500ft	320		Good separati ⁿ of Neph ^s Blue over Red - small ptcs
07:09:35	R5	100ft	330		
07:17:05	R5	100ft ↑			to coast in
07:19:25	R6	1500ft			
					Lower neph scat, and separati ⁿ
7:31:47	R6				Only Neph ^s is constant
07:33:32	R7	1500ft			Shot or run for SW
07:35	R7				end
					CDP 0.2 500
07:47:03	R7	1500ft			
07:47:56	R6/R8	100ft			Good Neph Seps
07:54:24	R8	100ft ↑	150		
		1000ft			into clld
		1500ft			taps of Cld
		2000ft			Sharp drop on Neph
07:55:44	R7	2500ft			Int
08:01:14	R7	"	330		rest


```
*** Opened channel log for #mevex at 08/05/2009 05:11:25
[2009/05/08 05:11] *** FAAMOpsDetach (~vircuser@85.154.2.202) has joined #mevex
[2009/05/08 05:11] <FAAM_flt_man> morning
[2009/05/08 05:11] [FAAMOpsDetach] leg tic thumbs up
[2009/05/08 05:12] [FAAMOpsDetach] going ok?
[2009/05/08 05:12] <FAAM_flt_man> nice one
[2009/05/08 05:12] [FAAMOpsDetach] top
[2009/05/08 05:12] [FAAMOpsDetach] everything all a-tanto?
[2009/05/08 05:12] <FAAM_flt_man> yes, just about to do orbit then into the sondes
[2009/05/08 05:12] [FAAMOpsDetach] top
[2009/05/08 05:13] <FAAM_flt_man> fwvs not getting ge data and no fwvs data on ORIS so far
[2009/05/08 05:13] [FAAMOpsDetach] strange
[2009/05/08 05:18] [FAAMOpsDetach] Doug says"did you find a battery pack"
[2009/05/08 05:19] <FAAM_flt_man> yes, i sent him a text. its in its cardboard box, in the mission
sci pickup box in the Oman Air store
[2009/05/08 05:26] [FAAMOpsDetach] 10:4. Just seen Doug who's been doing his dobie-ing and has now
retired for breakfast. I'll pas the message o
[2009/05/08 05:26] [FAAMOpsDetach] n
[2009/05/08 05:26] <FAAM_flt_man> fwvs problem looks like a connection one as horace not getting
response from send it an F
[2009/05/08 05:26] <FAAM_flt_man> thnax
[2009/05/08 05:28] <FAAM_flt_man> Joss suspects it is at fwvs rack
[2009/05/08 05:30] <FAAM_flt_man> will find out once the hypersonic wind tunnel is made safe
[2009/05/08 05:30] <FAAM_flt_man> and we can get up
[2009/05/08 05:40] [FAAMOpsDetach] ok. by the way, why did you mention flying inverted yesterday?
[2009/05/08 05:43] <FAAM_flt_man> cos the neph red was higher than the green was higher than the
blue which is upside down to normal
[2009/05/08 06:19] <FAAM_flt_man> scattering levels much lower today, around 250/m,
[2009/05/08 06:38] <FAAM_flt_man> Can you ask Dave K if there is a flight being planned for
tomorrow?
[2009/05/08 06:38] <FAAM_flt_man> If there isn't can he contact the ship to organise some tours of
the aircraft?
[2009/05/08 06:38] <FAAM_flt_man> chars
[2009/05/08 06:44] [FAAMOpsDetach] Dave's planning at the moment. The route we should follow is for
us to see tomorrow's flying requirements and then for Dave P to "formally" ask
if we can get the tours sorted out.
[2009/05/08 06:45] <FAAM_flt_man> is the forecast for strong dust event?
[2009/05/08 06:45] [FAAMOpsDetach] This is for two reasons (assuming no flight tomorrow) - 1. to
make sure that we can carry out any instrument work necessary;
[2009/05/08 06:46] [FAAMOpsDetach] 2. to keep Directflight involved.
[2009/05/08 06:46] <FAAM_flt_man> first we need Dave K to say go / no for a flight
[2009/05/08 06:48] <FAAM_flt_man> is there a problem there?
[2009/05/08 06:48] [FAAMOpsDetach] No.
[2009/05/08 06:48] <FAAM_flt_man> when is Dave going to make the decision re flying?
[2009/05/08 06:49] [FAAMOpsDetach] Dave's not finished planning yet (but prob no flight) but Pete
mentioned a bit of a worry about arrangements that haven't been asked for yet
[2009/05/08 06:50] [FAAMOpsDetach] Waiting for JT, but v soon
[2009/05/08 06:51] <FAAM_flt_man> okay, will wait for the decision then ask Dave P to make formal
request for tours
[2009/05/08 07:02] [FAAMOpsDetach] any update on the flight dust-wise?
[2009/05/08 07:02] [FAAMOpsDetach] Dave is tending heavily to no flight sat and prob no flight sun
[2009/05/08 07:02] [FAAMOpsDetach] but is still waiting for JT to get in (about 30 mins)
[2009/05/08 07:03] <FAAM_flt_man> scattering up to 250/m at 8k'
[2009/05/08 07:03] <FAAM_flt_man> just profiling down to 100' now, scattering picking up from 140/m
[2009/05/08 07:03] [FAAMOpsDetach] so still lower loadings (as expected) than yesterday
[2009/05/08 07:04] <FAAM_flt_man> yes, much
[2009/05/08 07:07] [FAAMOpsDetach] don't make too much of the "formal" by the way, just keping
everyone sweet!
[2009/05/08 07:09] [FAAMOpsDetach] Dave can ask via youself on here BTW, if you can also ask
whether there are any I want to work on my instruments type people once I let
u know the flying plans
[2009/05/08 07:09] <FAAM_flt_man> so no black tie and dapper slax then
[2009/05/08 07:11] <FAAM_flt_man> so far just sws needs to do a transfer cal
[2009/05/08 07:11] <FAAM_flt_man> if the decision is no for sat and sun, then the requirements will
probably be a bit different re instrument work
[2009/05/08 07:12] <FAAM_flt_man> ie joss and co need to put the instruments back as they were when
we left Cranners
[2009/05/08 07:15] <FAAM_flt_man> just found out we aren't recording PSAP. Wet neph using its
pump, did you know this?
[2009/05/08 07:22] [FAAMOpsDetach] no!
[2009/05/08 07:23] [FAAMOpsDetach] does this mean re-doing the processing?
[2009/05/08 07:25] <FAAM_flt_man> can you check the flcons file and see if !PSAP or NO PSAP
[2009/05/08 07:26] [FAAMOpsDetach] JT not at his desk yet.....!PSAP i'm afraid
[2009/05/08 07:26] <FAAM_flt_man> what does the "data" look like on flight plot?
[2009/05/08 07:29] [FAAMOpsDetach] nothing recorded on B446, B441 (as a quick sample)
```

[2009/05/08 07:30] <FAAM_flt_man> i'll check with Andy at end of flight if this has been the case for all mevex. if the data

[2009/05/08 07:30] <FAAM_flt_man> looks like nothing then maybe okay to note it in data quality file?

[2009/05/08 07:34] [FAAMOpsDetach] looks like it! Phew!

[2009/05/08 07:34] <FAAM_flt_man> good

[2009/05/08 07:35] [FAAMOpsDetach] I remeber his saying not to switch the PSAP switch on the core con, but didn't realise he was using it for the neph, i thought it was because he had the psap operation covered at the rack

[2009/05/08 07:36] [FAAMOpsDetach] This was at the campaign start, so expect the pump to have been used from the start

[2009/05/08 07:36] <FAAM_flt_man> okay. Was there a problem with PSAP?

[2009/05/08 07:40] [FAAMOpsDetach] no, I mean that I thought PSAP was i operatin at the rack

[2009/05/08 07:40] [FAAMOpsDetach] Dave on the phone to JT.....

[2009/05/08 07:43] <FAAM_flt_man> ...one thot re the tours is to taxy the airfcratt to Seeb north as it will be easier for the ship crew to get access there plus it will allow the RAF guys to have a look too

[2009/05/08 07:43] [FAAMOpsDetach] observers enjoying the flt?

[2009/05/08 07:44] [FAAMOpsDetach] yes, that's wot Pete was saying but he wasn't sure if anyone was doing anything about it

[2009/05/08 07:44] <FAAM_flt_man> its been a very bland flight so far, strapped in for most of the time so 'i hope they aren't too bored

[2009/05/08 07:44] [FAAMOpsDetach] if we do that, we will need aircon & GPU as well?

[2009/05/08 07:44] <FAAM_flt_man> alan foster has volunteered to do the driving, after Dave P and Joss offered

[2009/05/08 07:44] [FAAMOpsDetach] i bet he has

[2009/05/08 07:45] <FAAM_flt_man> ideally but that means getting the kit taken over from the civi side which will cost us (i don't know how much), maybe Pete can check

[2009/05/08 07:47] [FAAMOpsDetach] suppose we could not power the equipment but have the APU on for a cooling breeze

[2009/05/08 07:48] <FAAM_flt_man> yes.

[2009/05/08 07:49] [FAAMOpsDetach] dave still on th fone.....

[2009/05/08 07:50] <FAAM_flt_man> ...a long time to say non

[2009/05/08 07:51] [FAAMOpsDetach] i know

*** Closed channel log for #mevex at 08/05/2009 07:51:22

*** Opened channel log for #mevex at 08/05/2009 07:51:35

[2009/05/08 07:51] *** FAAMOpsDetach (~vircuser@85.154.2.202) has joined #mevex

[2009/05/08 07:51] [FAAMOpsDetach] oops

[2009/05/08 07:52] [FAAMOpsDetach] wot campaignshas Kate been campaign specialist for

[2009/05/08 07:53] <FAAM_flt_man> OP3

[2009/05/08 07:53] [FAAMOpsDetach] That's all i can think of as well

[2009/05/08 07:54] [FAAMOpsDetach] story is that the broad wx pattern is unchanging over the weekend, with no obvious big dusty event on the way

[2009/05/08 07:54] [FAAMOpsDetach] so tomorrow would be very like flights already done

[2009/05/08 07:55] [FAAMOpsDetach] so dave thinks hang on till Sunday to see if something pops up, but not thought likely

[2009/05/08 07:55] <FAAM_flt_man> is tht a no for tomorrow and a decide on sat for sun?

[2009/05/08 07:55] [FAAMOpsDetach] Not yet! Still on the fone. Patience....

[2009/05/08 07:56] [FAAMOpsDetach] what's patience?

[2009/05/08 07:56] <FAAM_flt_man> mighty

[2009/05/08 07:56] <FAAM_flt_man> girls name

[2009/05/08 07:56] <FAAM_flt_man> game of cards

[2009/05/08 07:56] <FAAM_flt_man> things they have in hospitals

[2009/05/08 07:56] [FAAMOpsDetach] wots a mighty?

[2009/05/08 07:57] <FAAM_flt_man> similar to a muckle

[2009/05/08 07:57] [FAAMOpsDetach] so that's clearer then....

[2009/05/08 07:58] <FAAM_flt_man> silightly less opaque anyway

[2009/05/08 07:58] [FAAMOpsDetach] oh no! Dave's had a quick thought!

[2009/05/08 07:58] [FAAMOpsDetach] I think we're going to fly.....

*** Closed channel log for #mevex at 08/05/2009 07:58:57

*** Opened channel log for #mevex at 08/05/2009 07:59:09

[2009/05/08 07:59] *** FAAMOpsDetach (~vircuser@85.154.2.202) has joined #mevex

[2009/05/08 07:59] <FAAM_flt_man> whats goin on?!

[2009/05/08 07:59] [FAAMOpsDetach] me pressing the wrong button

[2009/05/08 08:00] [FAAMOpsDetach] standby for official decision.....

[2009/05/08 08:00] <FAAM_flt_man> i mean with the fly / no fly / is it a bee

[2009/05/08 08:00] [FAAMOpsDetach] ...patience.....

[2009/05/08 08:02] <FAAM_flt_man> sitting on edge of seat

[2009/05/08 08:03] [FAAMOpsDetach] prob last nite's curry

[2009/05/08 08:04] <FAAM_flt_man> that and my frayed nerve

[2009/05/08 08:04] [FAAMOpsDetach] Question - do you have enough transport post-flight, does Phil need to come back across?

[2009/05/08 08:07] <FAAM_flt_man> we're okay, I'll come back with Kate. Is Doug out doing packup stuff?

[2009/05/08 08:08] <FAAM_flt_man> and the decision is.....?

[2009/05/08 08:09] <FAAM_flt_man> we're on the final run afore we profile out for home

[2009/05/08 08:11] [FAAMOpsDetach] fly tomorrow

[2009/05/08 08:11] <FAAM_flt_man> what are the details?
[2009/05/08 08:13] [FAAMOpsDetach] JT keen to do another flight tomorrow, prob 0900L t/o
[2009/05/08 08:13] [FAAMOpsDetach] A-train overpass at 1145 local as well
[2009/05/08 08:13] [FAAMOpsDetach] eta?
[2009/05/08 08:14] <FAAM_flt_man> eta 0925Z / 1325L ruffly
[2009/05/08 08:17] <FAAM_flt_man> please pass to dflops 'n engs, acknowlegde and copy
[2009/05/08 08:23] <FAAM_flt_man> Dave P would prefer to be on the ground tomorrow - crew thots
from that end?
[2009/05/08 08:30] <FAAM_flt_man> is there anybody there?
[2009/05/08 08:39] [FAAMOpsDetach] passed to ops etc
[2009/05/08 08:39] [FAAMOpsDetach] busy with other stuff
[2009/05/08 08:39] <FAAM_flt_man> nae bother
[2009/05/08 08:40] [FAAMOpsDetach] no crew thoughts yet, Dave's still writing the sortie brief
(quickly!)
[2009/05/08 08:40] <FAAM_flt_man> i've emailed doug.
[2009/05/08 08:40] <FAAM_flt_man> Updated ETA 1315L
*** Closed channel log for #mevex at 08/05/2009 09:16:45

Filter Sampling Log

Flight No:

B447

Date:

08-05-2009

Operator:

Type of filters mounted in	Top inlet	47 mm Nuclepore (0.4 µm pore size)	Bottom inlet	47 mm Nuclepore (0.4 µm pore size)
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Run No	Disk #1 TOP	Disk #2 MIDDLE	Disk #3 BOTTOM	Inlet Top/ Bottom	Time On	Time Off	Flight Run	Accum Vol [l]	Comments
Filters run1	B447-N45	----	----	Top					Blanks Filter top has been damaged
Filters run1	B447-N46	----	----	Bottom					
Filters run 2	B447-N47	----	----	Top	06:18:53	06:33:30		364	8200 ft Nephelometer values decreased during the SLR
Filters run 2	B447-N48	----	----	Bottom	06:18:53	06:33:30		597	
Filters run 3	B447-N49	----	----	Top	07:10:46	07:16:49		280	100 ft (above the sea)
Filters run 3	B447-N50	----	----	Bottom	07:10:46	07:16:49		375	
Filters run 3	B447-N51	----	----						Lab blank

Cloud Physics Flight Log B447

Date: 8/5/09	Operator: MAP	DRS Time: 02:30	DAU1 Time: +0	DAU2 Time: +0	AUX1 Time: +0	AUX2 Time: +0'
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DAU2 Disk space?

	PCASP SPP-200		CDP		PCASP		2DC		FFSSP		SID3	
Operated?					No						No	
Pre-flight checks	Vref	7.35	Ref V (~3):	2.69	Vref (>7):		El#1 V (>1):	-1.3	Ref V:	3.4	Comms?	No
	Sample flow	1.16			Flow (~1):		El#32 V (>1):	-1.3				
	Sheath flow	14.65			Pressure:							
					Temp (NDIT)							

GMT	Height	CDP		PCASP SPP-200		PCASP		2DC		Habit	FFSSP	SID3	Comments
		#/cc	MVD	#/cc	MVD	#/cc	Mean R	#/L	Max R				
04:48:00	FL180												Heaters on
05:00:45	FL290												Start Run 1.1
05:01:00				20	0.2						17		
05:03:00				20	0.2								
05:05:00				20	0.2								
05:07:00				20	0.2								
05:09:00				20	0.2								
05:11:00				20	0.2								
05:13:00				20	0.2								
05:15:12				Noise									End of Run
05:16:22													Start Orbits
05:18:43													End of Orbits
05:23:15													Start Run 2
05:24:00				20	0.2								
05:26:00				20	0.2								
05:28:00				20	0.2								
05:30:00				20	0.2								
05:32:00				20	0.2								
05:34:00				20	0.2								
05:36:00				20	0.2								
05:38:00				20	0.2								
05:40:00				20	0.2								
05:42:07													End of Run 2

GMT	Height	CDP		PCASP SPP-200		PCASP		2DC		Habit	FFSSP	SID3	Comments
		#/cc	MVD	#/cc	MVD	#/cc	Mean R	#/L	Max R				
05:50:29	FL290			20	0.2						18		Start Profile 1
05:51:45	FL280			30	0.2								
05:52:47	FL270			30	0.2								
05:53:46	FL260			35	0.2								
05:54:44	FL250			Spike									
05:55:33	FL240			30	0.2								
05:56:22	FL230			50	0.2								
05:57:10	FL220			45	0.2								
05:58:05	FL210			40	0.2								
05:59:04	FL200			40	0.2								
06:00:02	FL190			40	0.2								
06:01:05	FL180			30	0.2								
06:02:12	FL170			80	0.2								
06:03:10	FL160			100	0.2								
06:04:20	FL150	0.1	2	120	0.2								
06:05:18	FL140	0.1	2	200	1								
06:06:12	FL130	0.2	2	300	1								
06:07:06	FL120	0.2	2	150	1								
06:07:52	FL110	0.4	6	600	1.5								
06:11:15	FL100	0.3	8	500	1.5						19		
06:12:17	FL090	0.7	10	500	1.5								
06:13:24	FL080	0.8	10	600	2								Heaters off
06:14:11	FL070	0.7	10	500	2								
06:15:00	FL060	0.7	10	500	2								End of Profile 1 & Start Profile 2
06:16:09	FL070	0.7	10	550	2								
06:17:24	FL080												End of Profile & Start Run 3.1
06:18:00		0.8	10	600	2						20		
06:20:00		0.8	10	650	2								
06:22:00		0.8	10	700	2						21		
06:24:00		0.8	10	600	2								
06:26:00		0.8	10	750	2								
06:28:00		0.8	10	700	2						22		
06:30:00		0.8	10	650	2								
06:32:00		0.8	10	400	2								
06:33:29	FL080												End of Run & Start Profile 3
06:34:54	FL070	0.8	10	800	2						23		

GMT	Height	CDP		PCASP SPP-200		PCASP		2DC		Habit	FFSSP	SID3	Comments
		#/cc	MVD	#/cc	MVD	#/cc	Mean R	#/L	Max R				
06:36:02	FL060	0.8	10	800	2								
06:40:40	FL050	0.8	10	800	2								
06:41:52	FL040	0.7	10	500	2								
06:44:25	2500'												End of Profile & Start Run 4.1
06:45:00		0.4	10	500	2						25		
06:47:00		0.3	7	500	1.5								
06:49:00		0.2	5	300	1								Some large variations on pcasp
06:51:00		0.2	5	200	1								
06:53:00		0.2	5	200	1								
06:55:00		0.2	5	200	1						26		
06:57:00		0.15	5	200	1.5								
06:59:00		0.15	5	200	1.5								
07:00:35	2500'												End of Run & Start Profile 4
07:01:52	FL020	0.2	7	250	1								
07:04:16	FL010	1.2	10	700	1						27		
07:09:35	100'												End of Profile & Start Run 5
07:10:00		0.4	7	750	1								
07:12:00		0.6	7	700	1								
07:14:00		0.6	7	700	1						28		
07:16:00		0.5	7	700	1								
07:16:54	100'												End of Run & Start Profile 5
07:19:22	1500'												End of Profile & Start Run 6
07:20:00		0.3	7	600	1			0.5			29		
07:22:00		0.3	7	600	1			0.5					
07:24:00		0.2	7	600	1			0.5					
07:26:00		0.2	7	600	1			0.5					
07:28:00		0.2	7	600	1			0.5					
07:30:00		0.25	7	550	1								
07:31:46													End of Run
07:33:35	1500'												Start Run 7
07:34:00		0.3	7	550	1			0.5			30		
07:36:00		0.3	7	500	1			0.5					
07:38:00		0.25	7	550	1			0.5					
07:40:00		0.2	7	550	1			0.5					
07:42:00		0.2	7	550	1			0.5					
07:44:00		0.2	7	500	1			0.5			31		

GMT	Height	CDP		PCASP SPP-200		PCASP		2DC		Habit	FFSSP	SID3	Comments
		#/cc	MVD	#/cc	MVD	#/cc	Mean R	#/L	Max R				
07:46:00		0.2	7	550	1.5			0.5			31		
07:47:01	1500'												End of Run 7 start Profile 6
07:49:56	100'												End of Profile & Start Run 8
07:50:00		0.4	7	650	1								
07:52:00		0.4	7	650	1								
07:54:18	100'												End of Run & Start Profile 7
07:55:48	FL010	0.8	7	700	1						32		
07:57:46	FL020	0.5	7	400	1								
08:01:55	FL030	0.2	7	300	1								
08:03:07	FL040	0.2	7	300	1								
08:04:13	FL050	0.2	7	350	1						33		
08:05:27	FL060												End of Profile & Start Run 9
08:06:00		0.7	10	500	1								
08:08:00		0.8	10	500	1								
08:10:00		0.8	10	600	1								
08:12:00		0.8	10	600	1								
08:14:00		0.8	10	600	1						34		
08:16:00		0.8	10	650	1								
08:18:00		0.8	10	650	1						35		
08:20:00		0.8	10	650	1								
08:21:56													End of Run
08:25:50	FL060												Start Profile 8
08:26:58	FL070	0.8	10	650	1						36		
08:28:15	FL080	0.8	10	550	1								
08:29:10	FL090	0.8	10	500	1						37		
08:30:34	FL100	1.6	10	500	1								
08:31:29	FL110	0.8	10	400	1								
08:32:37	FL120	0.4	10	200	1								
08:33:40	FL130	0.4	10	150	1								
08:38:51	FL140	0.1	5	200	1								
08:39:44	FL150	0.1	5	100	1								
08:40:49	FL160	0.1	5	150	1								Heaters on
08:41:59	FL170			50	0.5								
08:43:03	FL180			50	0.5								
08:43:58	FL190			40	0.3								
08:44:56	FL200			40	0.3								End of Profile

Post flight

Instrument	Diagnostics		Brief report on instrument performance
PCASP (old)	Vref:		n.a
	Flow:		
2DC	EI#1:	-1.2	
	EI#32:	-1.2	
PCASP SPP-200	Ref V:	7.6	SWS noise and occasionally random noise
	Flow:	1.18	
CDP	Laser V:	4.07	Higher laser voltage at high altitude
FFSSP	Ref V:	3.2	Some random noise spikes at regular intervals
SID 3	Laser V:	N/a	
Rack Equipment		0.8GB	Please note SEADAS disk space remaining.

Flight:

B447

KEY

 Not Fitted

 Fitted, Not Operated

 Duff Data

 Minor Problem

 OK

Thermometers

Cabin Temperature:

Heimann:

Deiced Temp:

Non-deiced Temp:

Hygrometers

FWVS:

Buck CR2:

General Eastern:

Johnson Williams:

Nezvorov:

Total Water Probe:

Cameras

Downward Facing:

Forward Facing:

Rearward Facing:

Upward Facing:

Navigation + Aircraft

Cruciform GPS:

GIN Applanix:

INU Honeywell:

Radar Altimeter:

RVSM IAS:

RVSM Static Pressure:

XR5 GPS:

Misc Core

HORACE:

AMTG:

AVAPS:

Cabin Pressure:

Printer:

S9 Static Pressure:

Satcom C:

Satcom H (VIRC):

Turb Centre-Static:

Turb Left Right:

Turb Up-Down:

Turb Horizontal Chk:

Turb Vertical Chk:

Weather Radar:

DLUs:

DLU AERACK:

DLU BBR Lower:

DLU BBR Upper:

DLU Core Chem:

DLU Core Consoles:

DLU Port Aft:

DLU Port Fwd:

DLU Stbd Fwd:

Radiometers

Lower:

BBR (clear) Lower:

BBR (IR) Lower:

BBR (red) Lower:

Upper:

BBR (clear) Upper:

BBR (IR) Upper:

BBR (red) Upper:

ARIES:

DEIMOS:

IR Camera:

JNO2 Lower:

JNO2 Upper:

JO1D Lower:

JO1D Upper:

MARSS:

SHIMS Lower:

SHIMS Upper:

SWS:

TAFTS:

Cloud Probes

2DC:

2DP:

FFSSP:

PCASP:

PCASP SPP-200:

2DS:

ADA:

CAPS:

CCN:

CDP (fuselage):

CDP (Canister):

CIP 100 (PIP):

CIP 25 (CIP):

CPI:

CVI (Inlet):

CVI PCASP-X:

CVI Ly-A Hygro:

FSSP (UMan):

SID1:

SID2:

SID3:

Aerosol

CPC 3025A:

CPC 3786 H2O:

Filters 47mm:

Filters 90mm:

Neph - Dry:

Neph - Wet:

PSAP:

AMS:

CPC (AMS):

SMPS (AMS):

CPC 3010A (CVI):

INC:

Mini-LIDAR:

SP2:

UHSAS:

VACC:

Chemistry

CO Aerolaser 5002:

NOx TE42C:

Ozone TE49C:

Ozone TE49:

SO2 TE43C:

TDLAS (NIR) CH4:

TDLAS (NIR) CO2:

FAGE:

Formaldehyde:

NOx FAAM:

NOxy:

ORAC:

PAN:

PERCA:

Peroxide:

PTRMS:

TDLAS (1C):

WAS Bags:

WAS Bottles:

Misc Non-Core

CASI/ATM:

LIDAR (big):

LTI:

SAW Hygrometer:

Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B447

Date: 08 May 2009

Instruments

1. Core Console fwd – the keyboard trays have lots of sharp edges and corners. Arms partly shredded!
2. XR5M GPS – Receiver fault bit set on HORACE status page, otherwise looks okay. Fault bit cleared after takeoff.

3. RFC – no picture on fwd Core console video laptop, okay on the Aft Core Console. possible connection problem at rear quad box.

4. CPC – u/s, not operated.
5. GIN – serviceable
6. SATCOM-H: mpds service good
7. BBRs – Upper Pyrgeometer noisy for most of flight
8. Radalt – dropped to 0ft on HORACE at 063550, reset connection to DLU then okay

9. Cloud Physics - new pcasp noise from SWS 28V ? data
 - SID3 not operated
 - Old PCASP – u/s,(very noisy on Ch1), removed pre-flight
10. CVI – PCASP problem at start
11. IIR – misses chunks of data at low level. Wet Neph -
12. Dry Neph - okay
13. Nevzorov; failed sensor, not operated

14. Chemistry – okay cap on at FL290
15. AVAPS – 4 sondes launched. No. 3 – no data, sonde appeared to be stationary at 30kft after launch (operator error)

16. MARSS – okay
17. SWS/SHIMS - okay
18. ARIES – okay

19. Mini Lidar – okay, window dirty at end of flight
20. Filters – problem with one of the lines – when valves closed, still keeps counting.
21. FWVS – not receiving GE data or sending data to HORACE at start of flight. Tried reseating connections at FWVS and Corcon racks. Stop / Start H_FWVS, no change.
22. AMTG okay

Aircraft

Oil vapour smell when No 1 being started pre-flight. Cleared during the taxi.

Satcom-H Calls

nil

Post Flight - Turb Probe Water Traps

1. Indicate Amount of Water: a) Nil b) 1-2 drops c) ¼ full or more d) Ice present
2. Emptied by:
3. Dried by:

Pre-Flighter's Log

^ Clipboard power button

Date: 8/5/09

Flight No: B 447

Pre-Flighter: PHIL ROSENBERG

No.	✓ or x	Location	Action	Comments
1	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Hangar	Collect Dustbin, put on a/c	N/A
<u>Aircraft Cabin: Power-up</u>				
2	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Core Chemistry	Gases x 3 ON	OPERATOR
3	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Cabin	All Racks Checked	
4	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Fwd CorCon	All reqd CBs made	
5	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Aft CorCon	CBs made, PCs ON	
6	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	HORACE	Optical Disk loaded	
7	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	HORACE	Recording data	
8	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	HORACE	DLU Status Checked	
9	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	HORACE	HORACE Status Checked	
10	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Satcom H	Power LED ON	NOT RUNNING
11	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Nezvorov	Checked and OFF	NOT RUNNING
12	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	GPS	Checked	
13	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	INU	Align	N/A
14	<input type="checkbox"/>	Cameras Pictures	Checked x 4 OK	
15	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Core Chemistry	Instruments Checked OK	OPERATOR
16	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Core Chemistry	CO Flows Checked OK	OPERATOR
17	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	FWVS	Set up & check on AUTO	OPERATOR
18	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Video x 2	Records okay, Rewind	N/A
19	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Delced Rosemount	Heater Checked then OFF	
20	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Heimann	Calibration Checked	
21	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	TWC	ON & Checked	
22	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	GE	Balance checked	
23	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	INU	Navigate then back to Align	N/A

No.	✓ or x	Location	Action	Comments
24	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	CNC	Water filled Butanol filled	NOT RUNNING
25	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Dry Neph	Power up & Zero Cal	OPERATOR
26	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Miss. Sci Laptop	Checked Onboard	In cockpit
27	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	CGPS	CBs and PC ON	N/A
28	<input type="checkbox"/>			
<u>External Checks</u>				
29	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Turb Probe	Clean if reqd, Photo taken	
30	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	JW	Cleaned & Checked	
31	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	DI Rosemount	Cleaned & Checked	
32	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	NDI Rosemount	Cleaned & Checked	
33	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Nezvorov	Cleaned/windings checked	
34	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	GE	Cleaned & Checked	
35	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Lower BBRs	Domes cleaned/checked	
36	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Camera Windows	Cleaned	
37	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Heimann	Lens checked OK	
38	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	TWC Cover	Fitted if required	
39	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	All other covers	Removed	
40	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Dustbin	Returned to hangar	N/A
41	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Pre-flight Bag	Returned to hold	** Check no butanol**
42	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Tools	Check ALL in Toolkit	
43	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Tools	Avalon informed	
<u>Avalon Checks</u>				
44	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Upper BBRs Checked & Cleaned		Signed
45	<input type="checkbox"/>	ICEX applied		
46	<input type="checkbox"/>	Turb Probe - Traps emptied, detail contents -		a) Nil b) 1-2 drops c) 1/4 full or more
47	<input type="checkbox"/>	Turb Probe - Traps dried and resealed		

ARIES flight log

 Flight: B447

page 1 of 3

 Date: 08/may/09 Operator(s): S. ROGERS

 Res: 1

 Gain A: 2B: 2

 Loc./Notes: MEVEX: DUST

Scans: either "[IGMs]X[co-adds]", or "[stop DRS time]" if in start/stop, or "[macro name]". View: mirror angle.

DRS time	Flt ptrn	Scans	View	Shtr	HBB	CBB	Comments
0230	—						Power on OK
0435	TAKE OFF						
044520	FL158↑	cal	CH	0	81	42	CH cal macro.
045712	FL267↑	cal	CH	0	81	41	CH cal.
050058	FL290	cal	CH	0	81	41	CH cal.
050217	"	240x1	Z	0	81	41	Zenith
050314	"	360x1	N	0	81	41	Nadir
050618	"	cal	CH	0	81	41	CH cal.
050743	"	480x1	N	0	81	41	Nadir
051250	"	cal	CH	0	81	41	CH cal ← matching Sws.
051626	⁰¹ FL290	480x1	N	0	81	41	Nadir Orbit 40° left
051854	"	cal	CH	0	81	41	CH cal
052145	"	cal	CH	0	81	41	CH cal.
052313	FL290	480x1	N	0	81	41	Nadir Sonde.
052718	"	cal	CH	0	81	41	CH cal.
052850	"	480x1	N	0	81	41	Nadir Sonde. IASI 05332
0532—	"	120x1	N	0	81	41	Nadir ↙
053359	"	cal	CH	0	81	42	CH cal.
053515	"	60x1	Z	0	81	41	Zenith
053600	"	360x1	N	0	81	41	Nadir.
053848	"	cal	CH	0	81	41	CH cal.
054019	"	360x1	N	0	81	41	Nadir Sonde.
054219	"	cal	CH	0	81	41	CH cal
061217	8000 ⁱ	cal	CH	0	81	41	CH cal.
061706	"	cal	CH	0	81	40	CH cal.
061824	"	240x1	Z	0	81	41	Zenith
062015	"	240x1	N	0	81	41	Nadir Very murky
062216	"	240x1	N	0	81	40	Nadir Coast - sea → land 06:23:23
062347	"	cal	CH	0	81	41	CH cal
062505	"	480x1	Z	0	81	41	Zenith
0627—	"	240x1	N	0	81	41	Nadir

ARIES flight log

Flight: B447

page 2 of 3

Date:

Operator(s):

Res: 1

Gain A: 2 B: 2

Loc./Notes:

Scans: either "[IGMs]X[co-adds]", or "[stop DRS time]" if in start/stop, or "[macro name]". View: mirror angle.

DRS time	Flt ptrn	Scans	View	Shtr	HBB	CBB	Comments
06 29 -	8000'	cal	CH	0	81	42	CHcal.
06 30 37	"	240x1	Z	0	81	41	Zenith
06 33 -	↓ 8000	cal	CH	0	81	41	CHcal.
06 44 10	2800' ↓	cal	CH	0	81	41	CHcal. ↑
06 45 29	2500'	360x1	Z	0	81	42	Zenith Bumpy.
06 48 10	"	240x1	N	0	81	42	Nadir.
06 49 27	"	cal	CH	0	81	41	CHcal.
06 50 41	"	240x1	Z	0	81	42	Zenith
06 53 02	"	240x1	N	0	81	41	Nadir coast: land → sea.
06 55 -	"	cal	CH	0	81	41	CHcal.
06 56 28	"	480x1	Z	0	81	42	Zenith
06 58 26	"	240x1	N	0	81	42	Nadir
06 59 59	"	cal	CH	0	81	42	CHcal.
07 09	↓ 100'	cal	CH	0	81	43	CHcal. ↑
07 10 45	100'	240x1	Z	0	81	43	Zenith
07 12 36	"	240x1	N	0	80	43	Nadir Heiman cal.
07 14 02	"	240x1	Z	0	81	43	Zenith
07 14 45	"	cal	CH	0	81	44	CHcal.
07 16 08	"	240x1	Z	0	81	42	Zenith Pat 0716
07 17 07	↑ 300ft	240x1	N	0	81	43	Nadir coast: sea → land. 07 18 13
07 19 12	1500'	240x1	N	0	81	43	Nadir Bumpy.
07 20 57	"	cal	CH	0	81	43	CHcal.
07 22 18	"	120x1	Z	0	81	43	Zenith
07 23 41	"	360x1	N	0	81	43	Nadir
07 26 44	"	cal	CH	0	81	43	CHcal. Skill bumps.
07 28 -	"	240x1	Z	0	81	43	Zenith
07 29 12	"	240x1	N	0	81	43	Nadir
07 31 57	"	cal	CH	0	81	44	CHcal. ↓
07 33 38	1500'	N 3 min	N	0	81	43	Nadir 3 minute bumper.
07 39 21	"	120x1	Z	0	81	45	Zenith

Microwave Radiometers FLIGHT LOG		Date	08/05/09	Flight	B447	log pages
Operator(s)	Rob King		Campaign	MEVEX		
Departure			Arrival			

System start

MARSS

Visual pod inspection						•	
Close 3 SSP circuit breakers						•	
Close all MARSS circuit breakers						•	
FERA on	at time						
Temperature controller initial temps	Ch16	30°C	Ch	30°C	Ch18	29°C	
Temperature controller set points		54°C	17	58°C	-20	40°C	
MARSS CPU on	at time					0509	
Initial target temperatures	Hot		Cold				
Target heating						•	
*** CHECK SCAN HEAD CLEAR ***						•	
Scanning on (LMD box)	at time					0419	
Scan indication	Monitor			Visual			•

Deimos

Close all Deimos circuit breakers							
Turn on Deimos CPU							
*** CHECK SCAN HEAD CLEAR ***							
Start Deimos Software	at time						
Initial target temperatures	Hot		Cold				
Target heating							
Scan indication	Monitor			Visual			
Weather	Cloud		Precip				
	Surface		Pressure				
	Other						

System functionality check

(after initial system warmup, approx 1 hour)

PC to DRS Time error	$t_{PC}=t_{DRS} +$	0	at time			
Brightness temps 'sensible'						•
Target temps	MARSS:	Hot		Cold		
	Deimos:	Hot		Cold		
Channel gains 'sensible'	Ch1 A	Ch3 A	Ch1 B	Ch3 B		
	(-)	(-)	(-)	(-)		
	Ch16	Ch17	Ch18	Ch19	Ch20	
	(40-44)	(45-49)	(40-44)	(40-44)	(44-48)	

Power changeover

Headset on before start						•
Listen to engine start sequence	4, 3, 2, 1.					•
LMD off (3 switches, bottom to top)						•
Exit Deimos Software (x)						
POWER CHANGEOVER						
LMD on (3 switches, top to bottom)	then pushbutton					•
Restart Deimos Software						
System running again						at time

Southern Asia CAM Aerosol Optical Depth
At 06Z on 8/05/2009, from 12Z on 7/05/2009

AOD T+018

Southern Asia CAM Dust Concentrations
At 06Z on 8/05/2009, from 12Z on 7/05/2009

Dust concentration (leg1) T+018

Southern Asia CAM Horizontal Winds
At 06Z on 8/05/2009, from 12Z on 7/05/2009

700hPa Wind T+018

Southern Asia CAM Cloud
At 06Z on 8/05/2009, from 12Z on 7/05/2009

Total Cloud Cover T+018

Southern Asia CAM Aerosol Optical Depth
At 06Z on 8/05/2009, from 00Z on 7/05/2009

AOD T+030

Southern Asia CAM Dust Concentrations
At 06Z on 8/05/2009, from 00Z on 7/05/2009

Dust concentration (leg1) T+030

